

Anexo 1. Cadena de búsqueda de datos.

ERIC

title:(conception* OR misconception* OR difficulty OR difficulties OR misunderstanding*) AND (title:(astronomy OR "lunar phases" OR "moon phases" OR eclipse*) OR abstract:(astronomy OR "lunar phases" OR "moon phases" OR eclipse*)) AND (title:(student* OR teacher*) OR abstract:(student* OR teacher*))

SCOPUS

TITLE (conception* OR misconception* OR difficulty OR difficulties OR misunderstanding*) AND (TITLE (astronomy OR "lunar phases" OR "moon phases" OR eclipse*) OR ABS (astronomy OR "lunar phases" OR "moon phases" OR eclipse*)) AND (TITLE (student* OR teacher*) OR ABS (student* OR teacher*))

WEB OF SCIENCE

TI=(conception* OR misconception* OR difficulty OR difficulties OR misunderstanding*) AND (TI=(astronomy OR "lunar phases" OR "moon phases" OR eclipse*) OR AB=(astronomy OR "lunar phases" OR "moon phases" OR eclipse*)) AND (TI=(student* OR teacher*) OR AB=(student* OR teacher*))